

EFFECT ON PLANT NUTRIENT CONCENTRATION AND UPTAKE OF RICE AS INFLUENCED BY SOIL AND FOLIAR APPLICATION OF ZINC AND IRON IN RICE (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Abstract

A Field experiment was conducted in kharif season during 2021-22 on the field of Village Nuapur, Tal. Sadar, Dist. Balasore, (Odisha). through Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry College of Agriculture, Badnapur, VNMKV, Parbhani, with an objective to study the effect on plant nutrient concentration and uptake in rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) The experiment was conducted under Randomized Block Design (RBD) with the 7 treatments and 4 replications i.e., T₁-RDF, T₂-RDF+Nano Zinc(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS), T₃-RDF+Nano Fe (0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS), T₄-RDF + Nano Fe+Nano Zn(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS), T₅-RDF + ZnSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application), T₆-RDF+FeSO₄(25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application), T₇-RDF+ZnSO₄+FeSO₄(25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application). The result revealed that the concentration of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, zinc and iron in plant was significantly influenced due to different treatments. Amongst various treatments T₄ : RDF+ Nano Fe + Nano Zn(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS) recorded maximum N, P, K, Zn, Fe concentration in grain (1.22,0.29,0.38,33.6,62.56%) respectively, straw (0.43,0.11,1.48,23.7,106.20 %) respectively. Similarly the same treatment had noted highest total uptake (85.38, 20.39, 106.98, 301.59, 934.83 kg ha⁻¹) respectively, than other treatment however, which was statistically at par with treatment T₇: RDF+ZnSO₄+FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application).

Keywords: Zinc, Iron, Rice, Foliar application, 0.5 %, concentration, uptake.

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa*, L.) is one of the most important cereal crops of India, which is used as staple food by more than 70% of the population living in the Asian continent. It is extensively grown in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. The mineral elements most commonly lacking in human diets are iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn). In fact, rice is deficient of the above mineral elements. Since rice serves as staple food, even a minimum increase in nutritive value of rice can significantly impact human health (Chandel, 2010) [02]. Therefore, bio fortification breeding is stressed upon in many countries. Zn acts as catalytic or structural components of various enzymes involved in cellular metabolism. It promotes immunity, resistance to infections, growth and development of the nervous system, production of antibodies against intestinal pathogens. With even 20% Zn absorption and retention of 90 % in the blood serum, a daily ration of 422gm rice (having Zn conc. @ 28 mg Zn kg⁻¹ kernel) can supplement at least 25% of daily requirement. Reports are indicating high correlations between Zn deficiency tolerance and high grain Zn in rice, and hence, cultivation of Zn bio fortified rice seems to be rewarding in areas of Zn deficiency. Keeping in view the above facts, an attempt was undertaken to explore the status of grain Zn content in a set of selected rice genotypes and to assess its interrelationship with agro-morphological and quality traits.

Zinc (Zn) is one essential micronutrient for optimum growth and development of the crop plants and is required to be fortified in the crop produce. Which have key role in plants involved with enzymes and proteins in carbohydrate metabolism, protein synthesis, gene expression, auxin (growth regulator) metabolism, pollen formation, and maintenance of biological membranes, protection against photooxidative damage, heat stress, and resistance to infection by certain pathogens Zinc is a major component and activator of several enzymes involved in metabolic activities such as requirement for biosynthetic machinery of the respiratory system proteins cytochrome, structural proteins, and nucleotides, for proper gene expression, enzyme activation, and chlorophyll production, maintenance of membrane activity and improved seed and stalk. Zn content in food is very important for human health as the artificial supplementation of food with essential minerals is often difficult to achieve, particularly in developing countries.

Iron deficiency in rice mainly occurs under upland conditions; particularly in alkaline and calcareous soils. Sometimes severe chlorosis in rice due to Fe-deficiency has led to complete failure of rice crop (Katyal and Sharma, 1982) [05]. In most of the studies, foliar application of Fe has an edge over soil.

Nano fertilizers stand apart as one of the most helpful tool, because of their high productivity, functionalities, advantageous and simple applications. Nano fertilizer improve growth parameters of plants such as height of plants, leaf area, number of leaves per plant, increase in dry matter and chlorophyll, photosynthesis rate which outcome more translocation of photosynthets and production to various parts of the plant contrast to chemical fertilizers. Nanotechnology based nutrients could be more dissolvable or more receptive than their mass counterparts. Zinc nano fertilizers was found to continuous increase in dry matter, total fresh and dry mass of root and shoot of rice crop. Highest rate being shown with increasing level of zinc nano fertilizers, which might be recognized to improved responses of antioxidant in rice crop treated with zinc nano fertilizers.

Nano-fertilizers are nutrient carriers that are being developed using substrates with nano dimensions of 1 – 100 nm. Nano particles have extensive surface area and capable of holding abundance of nutrients and release it slowly and steadily such that it facilitates uptake of nutrients matching the crop requirement without any associated ill effects of customized fertilizer inputs reported that nano-fertilizers and nano composites can be used to control the release of nutrients from the fertilizer granules so as to improve the nutrient use efficiency while preventing the nutrient ions from either getting fixed or lost to the environment.

Material and Methods

A Field experiment was conducted in kharif season during 2021-22 on the field of Village Nuapur, Tal. Sadar, Dist. Balasore, (Odisha). through Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry College of Agriculture, Badnapur, VNMKV, Parbhani, with an objective to study the effect on plant nutrient concentration and uptake in rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) After completion of preparatory tillage operations the experiment was laid out in randomized block design (RBD) with seven (7) treatments as per plan. The layout consists of 28 experimental plots in four replications. The treatments comprises T₁-RDF, T₂-RDF+Nano Zinc (0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS), T₃-RDF+Nano Fe (0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS), T₄-RDF + Nano Fe+Nano Zn (0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS), T₅-RDF + ZnSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application), T₆-RDF+FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application), T₇-RDF+ZnSO₄+FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application).

Rice seed variety 'Swarna' was obtained from local cultivar which was prepared from previously grown crop, sown on 1st July, 2021. Firstly the seeds of paddy were sown in the nursery and after 15 days they were ready for transplanting in the main field as per randomly replicated plot having size 4.5 x 5.0 m² and 3.9m x 4.6 m² in gross and net plot size respectively, the seedlings were transplanted in the

main field following the spacing 15×15 cm². All the plots were fertilized with recommended dose of the NPK for rice was worked out according to the present recommendation of rice in coastal region of Odisha. The 100 (%) NPK dose in kg ha⁻¹ worked out was 100:60:60 for rice crop. The sources used for applying N, P, K, Zn and Fe were urea, single super phosphate, muriate of potash, ZnSO₄, FeSO₄, Nano Zn and Nano Fe. The crop was raised with all the standard package of practices and protection measures also timely carried out as they required. The crop of net plot area was harvested at physiological maturity stage on 02 December 2021, with the help of sickle. The crop was harvested close to ground and plant were tied in bundles and kept for sun drying on threshing floor for few days. After sun drying of harvested plants of net plot area are threshed by threshing machine.

For the determination of nutrient contents in plant samples fresh plant samples were collected various growth stages and grain sample at harvest and processed with following standard procedure of washing, sun drying and then oven drying and grinding. All the precautions were taken to avoid the contamination from other plant materials. The grind plant materials were stored in the paper bags and used for further chemical analysis. Grind material (0.5 g) was digested with 5 ml of di-acid mixture (HNO₃:HClO₄ in 9:4). It was kept in digestion chamber till complete digestion of the sample. The residue was dissolved in double-distilled water and after filtration; final volume was made to 50 ml. Nutrient content in plant and grain sample were analyzed for the total nitrogen content determined by Microkjeldahl's method A.O.A.C., (1965) [1], total phosphorus vanadomolybdo phosphoric acid yellow colour method spectrophotometrically as described by (Jackson, 1973) [04], total potash estimated by di-acid extract (Piper 1966) [07] by using flame photometer. The

iron and zinc content in grain and straw of rice were determined by DTPA method described by (Lindsey and Norvell, 1978) [06] with the help of atomic absorption spectrophotometer. Nutrient uptake (kg ha⁻¹) by using the following formula - {Nutrient uptake (kg ha⁻¹) = Nutrient content (%) X yield (kg ha⁻¹) / 100} and {Zn and Fe uptake (g ha⁻¹) = Nutrient content (mg kg⁻¹) X yield (kg ha⁻¹) / 1000}. The data collected from the above observation were analysed statistically by the procedure prescribed by Panse and Sukhatme (1967) [09]. The findings of the present study as well as relevant discussion have been presented under following heads.

Result and Discussion

Nutrient concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice

Nitrogen concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice

Data on content and uptake of nitrogen influenced by different soil and foliar

application of Zn and Fe at harvest are presented in table 1. Observations were recorded after harvest stage under different treatments. There was increase in N content in different plant parts with increasing levels of Zn and Fe application. Amongst various treatments maximum N content in grain and straw (1.22 and 0.43%) was observed under treatment T₄: RDF+ Nano Fe+ Nano Zn (0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS) which was followed by treatment T₇: RDF+ZnSO₄ + FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application) (1.20 and 0.41%). T₇ and T₂ were at par with T₄. Significantly lowest N content was recorded in grain and straw (1.13 and 0.37%) in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer. Similarly, highest uptake of N (85.38 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₄: RDF + Nano Fe + Nano Zn (0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS). T₇ and T₂ were at par with T₄.

Table No. 1 Nitrogen concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice

Treatments	N content (%)		N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		Total Uptake N (kg ha ⁻¹)
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	
T ₁ : Recommended dose of fertilizer	1.13	0.37	45.82	20.55	66.37
T ₂ : RDF+ Nano Zn(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	1.20	0.42	53.30	24.54	77.84
T ₃ : RDF+ Nano Fe(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	1.19	0.39	51.95	22.49	74.44
T ₄ : RDF + Nano Fe+Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS)	1.22	0.43	58.51	26.87	85.38
T ₅ :RDF+ZnSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	1.17	0.39	49.90	21.37	71.27
T ₆ : RDF+FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	1.15	0.38	48.67	21.05	69.72
T ₇ : RDF+ZnSO ₄ +FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	1.20	0.41	55.86	24.46	80.32
SE(m)±	0.038	0.091	0.135	0.134	0.445
CD at 5%	0.26	0.279	0.465	0.413	1.63

Lowest uptake of N (66.37 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer. The nitrogen concentration in rice plant was higher in grain than straw at harvest. This trend may be due to high mobility of nitrogen from vegetative tissues to reproductive organs after flowering stages. In presence of Zn and Fe, the increase in N uptake could be attributed to enhanced vigour of crop growth with increased utilization and translocation of N in to plant and synergetic effect between N and Zn and Fe in soil system resulting in the enhancement of yield. The enhance in N uptake may be due to availability of nitrogen to the crop and increase biomass production and loss of chlorophyll and leaf nitrogen with enhance photosynthesis and increased N supply during flowering and grain filling stage. The foliar nutrition of Zn and Fe increased the nitrogen availability in soil. Foliar form of Zn and Fe application was effective than soil application in content and uptake of nitrogen. Obtained results also confirmed with the finding of Tiwari (2020) [10] as there was 30%

increase in N content due to foliar application of micronutrients because of increase in metabolic activity in the plant.

Phosphorus concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice

Phosphorus content and its total uptake were influenced due to different treatments at harvest. Observations recorded after harvesting under different treatments are presented in table 2. There was increase in P content in different plant parts with increasing levels of Zn and Fe application. Maximum P content in grain and straw (0.29 and 0.111%) was observed under treatment T₄: RDF + Nano Fe + Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS) which was followed by T₇: RDF + ZnSO₄ + FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application) (0.27 and 0.109%). The lowest Phosphorus content was recorded in grain and straw (0.22 and 0.103%) in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer. Similarly, highest total uptake of Phosphorus (20.39 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₄: RDF+ Nano Fe+ Nano Zn

(0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS) (18.98 kg ha⁻¹) Significantly lowest uptake of Phosphorus (14.56 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer. T₇: RDF+ZnSO₄+FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application) (18.98) was at par with T₄. The phosphorus concentration in rice plant was higher in grain than straw at harvest. The increase in total uptake of P due to application of Zn and Fe might

be attributed to role of Zn and Fe in increasing the availability of soil phosphorus which might have increased the biomass and root activity.. Here foliar application was found to be more effective in P content and uptake. The result is also conformity with the findings of Pandey (2020) [08].

Table No. 2 Phosphorus concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice.

Treatments	P content (%)		P uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		Total Uptake P (kg ha ⁻¹)
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	
T ₁ : Recommended dose of fertilizer	0.22	0.103	8.83	5.37	14.56
T ₂ : RDF+ Nano Zn(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	0.26	0.107	11.54	6.27	17.81
T ₃ : RDF+ Nano Fe(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	0.24	0.105	10.50	6.07	16.57
T ₄ : RDF + Nano Fe+Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS)	0.29	0.111	13.72	6.67	20.39
T ₅ :RDF+ZnSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	0.25	0.106	10.66	5.80	16.46
T ₆ : RDF+FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	0.23	0.104	9.74	5.80	15.54
T ₇ : RDF+ZnSO ₄ +FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	0.27	0.109	12.47	6.51	18.98
SE(m)±	0.002	0.003	0.48	0.036	0.65
CD at 5%	0.008	0.009	1.56	0.09	1.87

Potassium concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice

Data on content and uptake of K showed non significant influence of different treatments at harvest. Observations recorded are presented in table.3. There was increase in K content in different plant parts with increasing levels of Zn and Fe application. Maximum K content in grain and straw (0.38 and 1.48%) was observed under treatment T₄: RDF+ Nano Fe+ Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS) which was followed by treatment T₇: RDF + ZnSO₄ +FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹soil application) recorded (0.36 and 1.47 %). Significantly lowest K content was recorded in grain and straw (0.31 and 1.39 %) in

treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer. Similarly, highest total uptake of K (106.98 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₄: RDF+ Nano Fe+ Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS) Significantly lowest uptake of K (89.93 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer.T₇ and T₂ were at par with T₄. The potassium per cent in rice plant was higher in straw than grain at harvest. Increased in the potassium uptake possibly might be due to stimulating effect of Zn and Fe on activation of H⁺-ATP as in the membrane. The results were also in confirmation with the findings of Tiwari (2020) [10] that there was increase in K content and uptake due to foliar application of nutrients.

Table No. 3 Potassium concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice.

Treatments	K content (%)		K uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		Total Uptake K (kg ha ⁻¹)
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	
T ₁ : Recommended dose of fertilizer	0.31	1.39	12.44	77.39	89.83
T ₂ : RDF+ Nano Zn(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	0.35	1.44	15.54	84.45	99.99
T ₃ : RDF+ Nano Fe(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	0.34	1.42	14.87	82.17	97.04
T ₄ : RDF + Nano Fe+Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS)	0.38	1.48	17.98	89.00	106.98
T ₅ :RDF+ZnSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	0.33	1.45	14.07	79.38	93.45
T ₆ : RDF+FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	0.32	1.46	13.56	81.52	95.08
T ₇ : RDF+ZnSO ₄ +FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	0.36	1.47	16.63	87.90	104.53
SE(m)±	0.001	0.023	0.44	0.87	3.05
CD at 5%	0.003	0.087	1.87	2.89	9.98

Zinc concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice

Data on content and uptake of Zinc influenced by different soil and foliar application of Zn and Fe are presented in table 4. Zn content and uptake was significantly influenced by due to soil and foliar application of Zn and Fe at harvest. . There was increase in Zn content in different plant parts with increasing levels of Zn and Fe application. Amongst various treatments maximum Zn content in grain and straw (33.6 and 23.7 mg kg⁻¹) was observed under treatment

T₄: RDF +Nano Fe+ Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS). T₇: RDF+ZnSO₄ + FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application) (32.0 and 22.3 mg kg⁻¹) was at par with T₄. Significantly lowest Zn content was recorded in grain and straw (27.7 and 15.3 mg kg⁻¹) in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer. Similarly, significantly highest uptake of Zn (301.59 g ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₄: RDF + Nano Fe+ Nano Zn (0,5% foliar spray at 30 DAS) Zn (278.20 g ha⁻¹). Significantly lowest uptake of Zn (196.43 g ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer

Table No. 4 Zinc concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice.

Treatments	Zn content (%)		Zn uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		Total Uptake Zn (kg ha ⁻¹)
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	
T ₁ : Recommended dose of fertilizer	27.7	15.3	111.24	85.19	196.43
T ₂ : RDF+ Nano Zn(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	31.8	20.9	141.25	122.57	263.82
T ₃ : RDF+ Nano Fe(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	29.7	17.6	129.96	101.85	231.81
T ₄ : RDF + Nano Fe+Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS)	33.6	23.7	159.06	142.53	301.59
T ₅ :RDF+ZnSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	30.5	19.6	130.08	107.31	237.39
T ₆ : RDF+FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	29.1	18.6	123.32	103.86	227.18
T ₇ : RDF+ZnSO ₄ +FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	32.0	22.3	147.84	130.36	278.20
SE(m)±	0.34	0.32	1.96	2.02	2.42
CD at 5%	1.65	1.45	5.76	6.54	6.89

The Zn concentration in rice plant was higher in grain than straw at harvest. This trend may be due to high mobility of Zn from vegetative tissues to reproductive organs after flowering stages. In presence of Zn and Fe, the increase in Zn uptake could be attributed to enhanced vigour of crop growth with increased utilization and translocation of Zn into plant and synergetic effect between Zn and applied nutrients in soil system resulting in the enhancement of yield. The enhance in Zn uptake may be due to availability of nitrogen to the crop and increase biomass production. The foliar nutrition of Zn and Fe increased the Zn content and uptake more than soil application. Obtained results also confirmed with the finding of Dash and Patro (2010) [103]. Their findings suggested that there was 5-10% more uptake of Zn due to foliar application of Zn than soil application.

Iron concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice

Data on content and uptake of Iron influenced by different soil and foliar application of Zn and Fe are presented in table 5. Fe content and uptake was significantly influenced due to soil and foliar application of Zn and Fe of different treatments at harvest. Amongst various treatments significantly maximum Fe content in grain and straw (62.56 and 106.20 mg kg⁻¹) was observed under treatment T₄: RDF+ Nano Fe+ Nano Zn (0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS) which was followed by treatment T₇: RDF+ZnSO₄+FeSO₄ (25 kg ha⁻¹ soil application) (61.52 and 105.40 mg kg⁻¹). Significantly lowest Fe content was recorded in grain and straw (52.06 and 98.72 mg kg⁻¹) in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer. Similarly, significantly highest uptake of Fe (934.83 g ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₄: RDF+ Nano Fe+ Nano Zn (0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS). Significantly lowest uptake of Zn (758.74g ha⁻¹) was recorded in treatment T₁: Recommended dose of fertilizer. The Fe concentration in rice plant was higher in straw than grain at harvest.

Table No. 5 Iron concentration and uptake of rice as influenced by soil and foliar application of Zinc and Iron in rice.

Treatments	Fe content (%)		Fe uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)		Total Uptake Fe (kg ha ⁻¹)
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	
T ₁ : Recommended dose of fertilizer	52.06	98.72	209.07	549.67	758.74
T ₂ : RDF+ Nano Zn(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	55.62	101.88	244.39	597.52	841.91
T ₃ : RDF+ Nano Fe(0.5% foliar spray at 30 DAS)	59.89	104.45	262.07	604.45	866.52
T ₄ : RDF + Nano Fe+Nano Zn (0.5%foliar spray at 30 DAS)	62.56	106.20	296.15	638.68	934.83
T ₅ :RDF+ZnSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	54.78	100.38	233.63	549.58	783.21
T ₆ : RDF+FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	58.40	103.12	247.49	575.82	823.31
T ₇ : RDF+ZnSO ₄ +FeSO ₄ (25 kg ha ⁻¹ soil application)	61.52	105.40	284.22	630.29	914.51
SE(m)±	0.71	1.001	1.42	2.46	3.48
CD at 5%	2.13	3.23	3.76	8.67	10.76

This trend may be due to high mobility of Fe from reproductive organs to vegetative tissues. In presence of Zn and Fe, the increase in Fe uptake could be attributed to enhanced vigour of crop growth with increased utilization and translocation of Fe into plant and synergetic effect between Fe and applied nutrients in soil system resulting in the enhancement of yield. The enhance in Fe uptake may be due to availability of nitrogen to the crop and increase biomass production. The foliar nutrition of Zn and Fe increased the Fe content and uptake more than soil application. Obtained results also confirmed with the finding of Tiwari and Shahid (2010) [111].

Conclusion

The present study concluded that rice performed the best with the application of Nano Zn and Nano Fe through foliar mode along with recommended dose of NPK (100:60:60 kg ha⁻¹) (T₄) effective to its advantageous for enhancing nutrient content and uptake of nutrients in rice.

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